

Analysis of mining- induced terrain deformation phenomena using a direct integration PSInSAR approach

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Underground mining activity often triggers substantial ground surface displacements both vertical, i.e. subsidences, and horizontal directions. This work is devoted to illustrate a method that employs satellite radar interferometry to extract the vertical and horizontal components of the ground surface deformations along the radar line-of-sight (LOS). Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) has been employed to study terrain deformation for decades and has seen relevant developments in terms of accuracy and coverage with the introduction of techniques based on persistent scatterers (Persistent Scatterer InSAR, PSInSAR).

The availability of SAR datasets with increasing spatial and temporal coverage, with decreasing temporal intervals between two subsequent acquisitions, such as the ones collected by the Copernicus Sentinel-1 constellation, gives the opportunity to analyse and monitor ground-surface deformation phenomena, of natural origin (such as landslides) or man-induced.

In this work, we employ on a satellite SAR dataset collected by the Sentinel-1 A&B sensors, using the interferometric wide swath (IW) acquisition mode and both descending and ascending pass. Vertically polarized transmit-receive (VV) data were analysed, as they are expected to provide a higher PS coverage with respect to other polarisations. The area of interest (AOI) is located around the town of Polkowice, south-western Poland, and is delimited by a rectangle whose North-West and South-East vertices have coordinates (51° 30' 25.49801" N, 16° 1' 7.62359"E) and (51° 28' 51.15166" N, 16° 8' 23.57851" E), respectively. The presence of copper mines within the AOI causes ground-surface deformations, with both a vertical component (subsidence) and horizontal component, detectable in the East-West direction.

The main processing steps leading to the formation of the PS grid consist of (i) image coregistration; (ii) interferogram generation, achieved using a direct integration approach, i.e. each interferogram is generated from two subsequent images; (iii) multilooking, using a window whose azimuth and range lengths are 2 and 10, respectively, yielding a pixel size of about 28 m in azimuth and 23 m in range; (iv) PS selection, based on a coherence threshold of 0.4; (v) phase unwrapping; (vi) time series generation; (vii) removal of the Atmospheric Phase Screen, which is previously estimated using a combination of spatial low-pass and temporal high-pass filters; (viii) geocoding. This procedure was applied to both Ascending and Descending data, thus enabling the extraction of time series of the East-West (EW) and Up-Down (UD) displacements.

The analysed datasets were collected by the Sentinel-1 constellation in two different blocks, the first one from September 19, 2019 to February 5, 2020 and the second block from February 5 to June 28, 2020, with an interval of six days between two subsequent acquisitions. The size of the AOI, after multilook processing, was equal to 260 rows and 255 columns, containing about 11000 detected PSs. Within the AOI, several trihedral corner reflectors were located in order to increase the number of detected PSs with very high coherence.

The results show the presence of three main areas that are affected by ground surface deformation. The UD component of the linear velocity reaches maximum values of about 40-50 mm/year, common to all the affected areas, whereas the EW horizontal component is maximum for the area at the south of Polkowice (about 30 mm/year eastward) and almost null for the other areas. In addition to the geocoded time series, a quality-index map was calculated as the standard deviation of the residuals of the velocity estimation, which was previously extracted as the linear fit that best approximates the deformation time series. Such quality index usually presents high values if the phase noise of the PS point is high or if the deformation is non-linear.

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